

Biomathematics and Extensive Quantum Statistics of DNA and Biology

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Abstract

First, some specific biomathematics is introduction. Next, two new mathematical methods are applied in biology, both are the simple joint relation of algebra in set theory, and the tree-field representation and the extensive Feynman diagrams in the graph theory. Third, the Cambrian life explosion originated from unicellular to bicellular to multicellular, so we propose that it can be explained by chaos. Fourth, based on the extensive quantum biology and the biological particles, we propose the extensive quantum statistics of DNA and biology, and corresponding quantum equations. Fifth, we discuss some new research of biology, such as the biological QED and QCD. Various levels in the biological systems have all laws with randomness and statistics, for which the most similar physical theory will be general quantum theory.

Keywords: *biology, mathematics, quantum, statistics, DNA, Cambrian life explosion.*

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Introduction

Biomathematics is the use of mathematical models to help understand phenomena in biology. Modern biology is very good at taking biological systems apart (at all levels of organization, from genome to global nutrient cycling), into components simple enough that their structure and function can be studied in isolation. Dynamic models are a way to put the pieces back together, with equations that represent the system's components, processes, and the structure of their interactions.

Mathematics in biology and medicine is an important developed direction, for example, the topological biology (Rashevsky, 1954,1955; Babtie, et al. 2014). Mathematical models are also important tools in many areas of biology, including physiology, ecology, evolution,

toxicology, immunology, natural resource management, and conservation biology. The result obtained from analysis and simulation of system models are used to test and extend biological theory, and to suggest new hypotheses or experiments. Models are also widely used to synthesize available information and provide quantitative answers to practical questions. Biomathematics is not a narrow discipline, in fact it encompasses all of biology and virtually all of the mathematical sciences, including statistics, and scientific computing, etc.

Mathematics in biology has two characteristics: diversity and novelty (Stewart, 2011). Fung (1981) and Nigg, et al. (1999), investigated biomechanics, which includes the mechanical properties of bone, cartilage, ligament, tendon, muscle, the neuro-musculo-skeletal system, and biomaterials, etc. Levitov (1991) and Shipman, et

al. (2004), researched phyllotaxis on plants by flux lattices, etc. This determines Phyllotactic Fibonacci numbers or Lucas numbers. In this paper, some specific biomathematics is discussed, the Cambrian explosion is explained by chaos, and the extensive quantum statistics of DNA and biology is proposed.

Some Specific Biomathematics

The focus of biomathematics program is on building and using mathematical models to describe and analyze biological systems. Often this involves the analysis of biological data, which typically means using statistical approaches together with the models. In many cases, these models are mechanistic, meaning that their components represent biological processes.

Based on the inseparability and correlativity of the biological systems, we proposed the nonlinear whole biology and four basic hypotheses (Chang 2012b). It may unify reductionism and holism, structuralism and functionalism, and is consistent with the systems biology. Further, the loop quantum theory is applied to biology, and proposed the model of protein folding and lungs, and obtain four approximate conclusions (Chang 2012b).

Wilson-Cowan coupled nonlinear differential equations describe interactions of much interconnected neurons (Wilson et al. 1972). The equations are derived for the dynamics of spatially localized populations containing both excitatory and inhibitory model neurons.

Generally, biomechanics should be nonlinear. In nonlinear mechanics there are strange attractors and chaos. Cushing, et al., discussed chaos in ecology (Cushing, et al. 2002).

In biology and physiology there are widely various chaos and fractal (Chang 2013c) and the nonlinear dynamics. They include the excited or stimulated state of neuron and whose Hodgkin-Huxley equation (Aihara, et al. 1984), and the heart beats rhythmically and whose Bonhoeffer-Van der Pol equation (Fitzhugh 1969), and the exudation of hormone, and the dynamical disease and epidemic, and the complex structure of living systems (Cramer, 1988), etc. Hartline equation in the inhibitory neural network may

add the nonlinear terms, and then chaos will appear. Life seeks the optimum rather than the maximum. It corresponds to the optimum mathematics. But, the maximum may lead to the demise of the system, such as from dinosaurs to corrupt officials.

The proteins are composed of molecules with both amino (-NH₂) and carboxyl (-COOH). The 3D structure of proteins is a critical challenge (Wales, 2004). Their folding structures are that various interactions bring the system free energy to a minimum. Lennard-Jones potential

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n (r_{ij}^{-12} - 2r_{ij}^{-6})$$
 determines the configuration of the minimum cluster of potential energy atoms. Combined with the computer, in 1987 Northby for n=13-147 gives the minimum value of this potential energy.

The theoretical basis of the traditional Chinese medicine is Yin-Yang and Five-Element theory. Both mathematics are respectively the two-element replacement group and the five-element circular group SO(5) (Chang 1989). We discussed space of Five Elements-Eight Trigrams in the traditional Chinese medicine, and proposed the pharmaceutical matrix mechanics (Chang 1995). Further, we introduced the diagnostic space, treatment space and some medicinal vectors, and proposed the matrix mechanics of pharmacology, and corresponding linear algebra and quantum medicine (Chang 1995,2021). Based on the Chinese traditional culture, we proposed three principles of self-cultivation and health: health must first nourish self-heart, life should be a combination of movement and peace, and the body-mind-spirit union. We researched also the preliminary epidemic equations of COVID-19, and discussed their meaning (Chang 2023).

Memory may be combined with the elastic mechanics. We researched the nonlinear mechanism of memory (Chang 2012b). Short-term memory corresponds to shallow nicks and can be recovered; long-term memory corresponds to deep nicks and cannot be recovered. Moreover, there are implicit or overt memories. A nonlinear Lorenz model may be applied to describe the model of brain (Chang 2013a,2023).

Two New Mathematical Methods Applied in Biology

It is known that biomechanics is not mechanics of rigid body. Since the same force acts at different points for biology, results are bigger difference, such as the action-point of the enzyme. It may be expressed by $F(p, B)$. Usual blood as an incompressible non-Newtonian fluid applies hydrodynamics (Burton 1965; Rushmer 1970; Caro et al. 1978), and is related with biorheology (Blair 1974). Bone corresponds to a classical linear elastic theory (Cowin 1981). Biomembrances are researched from mechanics and thermodynamics (Evans et al. 1980). Therefore, scalar and vector are applied widely in biology. Antonelli, et al. (1993), discussed the theory of sprays and Fisler spaces and their applications in physics and biology.

For two any sets M and N , we researched the simple mathematical joint relation of algebra in set theory:

$$(M, k)(k', N) = (M, kk', N), \quad (1)$$

and discussed its some properties. It may describe various relations among sciences and many intersecting sciences (Chang 2017a). This is applied to various aspects in natural science and social science, which includes transcription, splicing and replication, etc., in biology, and both main relations in micro-economics and macro-economics, etc. Further, it may be corrected and developed.

In biology the simple joint relation corresponds to various chain structures, which include proteins and nucleic acids. It can describe the inheritance, translation, replication, etc. The photosynthesis is:

Its reverse process is that fireflies and other luminous objects use ATP and oxygen to produce light and carbon dioxide.

In biology enzymes act as catalysts. For example, carbonic anhydrase is:

Generally, in the dynamics of proteins catalysis is the induced-fit and lock-and-key mechanism.

In cell biology cell division is $g(k, C) = (C_1, j)C_2$, or $= \begin{pmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \end{pmatrix}$, here g is growth.

The protein conformations have four levels of structure (Fig.1): 1). Primary structure simply refers to the sequence of the different amino acids of the peptide or protein, which is held together by covalent or peptide bonds, which are made during the process of protein biosynthesis or translation. 2). Secondary structure is the general three-dimensional form of local segments of biopolymers such as proteins and nucleic acids (DNA/RNA) in molecular biology and structural biology. The secondary structures of peptides have one of two forms, α helix or β sheet. The α helix is a helical twisting of the polypeptide. α helix and β sheet involve interaction of the N-H of an amino acid with oxygen. It is namely the hydrogen bond. 3). Tertiary structure is the larger and more complicated conformation of the whole polypeptide. 4). Quaternary structure.

In modern molecular biology (Malacinski et al. 2003; Weaver 2005; Alberts et al. 2007) in order to make proteins, DNA is copied using another nucleic acid (RNA), which is transcription process. Its first step is gene expression, in which a particular segment of DNA is copied into RNA (especially mRNA) by the enzyme RNA polymerase. During transcription, a DNA sequence is read by an RNA polymerase, which produces a complementary, antiparallel RNA strand called a primary transcript.

Transcription proceeds in the following general steps: RNA polymerase binds to promoter DNA, and creates a transcription bubble, which separates the two strands of the DNA helix. This is done by breaking the hydrogen bonds between

complementary DNA nucleotides. RNA polymerase adds RNA nucleotides, and RNA sugar-phosphate backbone forms with assistance from RNA polymerase to form an RNA strand. Hydrogen bonds of the RNA-DNA helix break, freeing the newly synthesized RNA strand. If the cell has a nucleus, the RNA may be further processed. This may include polyadenylation, capping and splicing. The RNA may remain in the nucleus or exit to the cytoplasm through the nuclear pore complex. When mRNA synthesis refers to from an RNA molecule, it is namely RNA replication, for instance, a viral RNA replicase (Koonin et al. 1989).

Figure 1. Protein Structure from Primary to Quaternary Structure

Its mechanism is represented by figures of three different phases.

1) **Initiation.** Transcription begins with the binding of RNA polymerase (RNAP) as a core enzyme to the promoter in DNA.

Figure 2. Simple Diagram of Transcription Initiation

2) **Elongation.**

Figure 3. Simple Diagram of Transcription Elongation (RNA in Blue Color)

3) **Termination.**

Fig.4. Simple Diagram of Transcription Termination. RNA is Shown in Blue Color.

We try to represent transcription by the simple form: Core enzyme (holoenzyme) joins the promoter $e(p,D)=(D,R,D)e$, here e is enzyme (RNAP), and p is promoter, then by $(D,R,D)=(D,R)(R,D)=D'$. It has two types: intrinsic $(D,D')R$ and ρ (Rho protein)-dependent $\rho(D,D')=(D,D')R$.

Gene expressions under different conditions A and B are (Malacinski et al. 2003):

$$\begin{pmatrix} A \\ B \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A_1, A_2, A_3 \\ B_1, B_2, B_3 \end{pmatrix} = (C_1, C_2, C_3). \quad (4)$$

The lactose metabolism is $\beta(La)=(Ga,Gl)$. In regulation of gene expression the lac repressor binds to the operator in the regulatory upstream region of the operon. It is namely $lac(o,G)$ and $CAP(p,o)=(cAMP-CAP-complex,T)$.

Splicing is the process by which pre-mRNA is modified to remove certain stretches of non-coding sequences called introns; the stretches that remain include protein-coding sequences and are called exons. Sometimes pre-mRNA messages may be spliced in several different ways, allowing a single gene to encode multiple proteins. This process is called alternative splicing. Splicing is usually performed by an RNA-protein complex called the spliceosome, but some RNA molecules are also capable of catalyzing their own splicing (Fig.5). Splicing reaction of gene is:

$$e_1(i, e_2, G) = (e_1 e_2, G) i, \quad (5)$$

here e is exon and i is intron.

Figure 5. Simple Illustration of a Pre-mRNA, with Introns (top). After the Introns have been Removed via Splicing, the Mature mRNA Sequence is Ready for Translation (Bottom)

RNA is used as a guide to put together the small molecules that make protein, which is translation process. This general progression (the central dogma) $DNA \rightarrow RNA \rightarrow Protein$ is used in all life forms.

Mechanism of translation is: For prokaryotes, first the initiation is $itR(sc, G)=(IF, G)$, here itR is initiator tRNA, sc is start codon, and IF is

translation initiation factors. Then elongation and termination are

$$itR(p,G)=(p')itR(A,G)=(p',A')itR(B,G)=\dots=(G')sc, \quad (6)$$

here sc is stop codon.

The main types are: the helix-turn-helix structure, the zinc finger structure, the helix-loop-helix, (HLH) structure and the leucine zipper structure, etc. They are

$$(R,k)(k',P)=(R, j_i, P), \text{ and } kk' = j_i \ (i=1,2,3,4). \quad (7)$$

Every cell in the human body contains exactly the same DNA. But, different cell types possess completely distinct functions and forms due to proteins determined by gene expression.

The genetic code may be an amino acid group with four U,C,A,G and three amino acid group with 64, which is a codon. Both correspond just to Four-Phases in Chinese Yi, and 64 Hexagrams (Guas), which is also codon of world. Therefore, Chinese traditional culture supposed that a body is a small universe, and Universe is a large body.

In DNA replication the semi-conservative replication is that each double-stranded DNA after replication conserves one parent strand but adds one new daughter strand. It is:

$$p(o, D_p) = \begin{pmatrix} D_1 \\ D_2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

Different sensation systems are usually independent each other. Our collective open out the potential of blind children, and found through a period training of time, some children by touch or nose or ear can distinguish different colors, numbers and various figures. From this and other research, we proposed a hypothesis: The neural excitable cell is continuously induced and excited, then grow out new synapse and

dendrite, and the feeling system, hearing system, smell system, etc., may joint to visual system, and form a new neural network, and achieve finally a transformation among vision and other sensations. It is expressed by $nec(k,B)=(vn,B)$, here nec is neural excitable cell, and vn is new visual network. Further, we proposed some possible tests, for example, for trained mammal, etc., and researched possible theories (Chang 2013b; 2017b). It is a testable application of the nonlinear whole neurobiology.

A graph is a pair $G=(V,E)$ of sets. The elements of V are the vertices (or nodes, or points), and the elements of E are its edges (or lines) (Diestel 2000). We extended the tree in the graph theory to a new tree-field representation, which includes two parts: tree and field (Fig. 6) (Chang 2014b):

Figure 6. Tree-Field Representation

Here the fields (C and S, etc.) are some sets of much small trees, which are also trees under microscope. Fields and trees can transform each other. This is a unification of clear simplicity (tree) and indistinct complexity (field), and may be applied to various complex systems on science, politics, economy, philosophy and so on. Further, it may be extended to the whole graph theory $G=(V,E,F)$, here F is a set of small graphs (Chang 2014b). For taxonomy and taxonomic system trees, field may correspond to a large class of indistinguishable species.

Each system of the body is tree-field bound, the tree is connected, and the field is the key. For example, lung is field in the respiratory system,

heart is field in the blood system, brain is fielding the nervous system, in the visual system eye and brain are fields at both ends, etc.

In the quantum theory of fields Feynman represented a set of particles with interacting fields, and proposed a set of graphical rules for calculating S-matrix elements (Feynman 1948;1949; 1962).

The simplest Feynman diagrams (graphs) only consist of vertex and straight line. Their structure is completely the same with digraph theory. Further, Feynman diagrams apply that straight lines represent fermions, dotted lines represent bosons, and wavy lines represent photons. New tree-field representations in graph theory combines Feynman diagrams and their extension, we proposed developments in graph theory (Chang 2014c). Mathematically, it may include five types of the basic elements: various solid lines (E), dotted lines (D) and wavy lines (W), which correspond to the edge-induced spanning-tree in some graphs, and vertices (V), fields (F). Here field is not a simple loop, and is an extension of vertex with complex connotation. Dotted line and wavy line are two extensions of line, which represent different joins. These lines may have slope, and form various closed cycles, etc. In topology they belong to still vertices and edges.

In the new graph theory $G=(V(V,F), E(E,D,W))$, or $G=(V,F; E,D,W)$. The degree of a vertex v is the number $|E(v)|$ of edges at v . They may be a digraph (directed graph) $D=(V,A)$, where $V(D)$ is vertex set and $A(D)$ is arc set (Bang-Jensen, et al. 2002). The order is a number of vertex, and the size is a number of arc. A undirected graph $G=(V,E)$, where $V(G)$ is vertex set and $E(G)$ is edge set. It may be extended to the degree of a field. Coloring (vertex k -coloring and edge k -coloring) and flows are known in graph theory (Jensen, et al. 1995). Moreover, there have the double line (solid, dotted or wavy), the three lines and n -lines, and vertices may be transition point, etc. We researched the meanings of various basic elements (Chang 2014c). Various edges may be directed arcs or undirected edges. Both may be respectively directed time and undirected space. These elements may be coloring and be

weighted, which represents time or spatial distance, or flow, etc. Fractal may be isomorphic, but be different weighted (Bollobas 2002). Further, they may be in 3-dimensional and higher-dimensional real space and time even higher-dimensional complex space-time. And these lines may be developed to various tubes, and these vertices may be developed to various balls in n-dimensional space.

It is known that biology includes: cytology, genetics, physiology, biochemistry, biophysics, molecular biology, biotechnology, environmental biology and ecology, immunology, microbiology, botany, zoology, entomology, anthropology and pharmacology, etc. We may apply the new extensive graph theory to various complex structures and joins, for example, DNA. Bones are lines and tubes. Assume that cells correspond to fields, and various fibres correspond to different lines. The stomach is field, so intestine is line and 3-dimensional tube.

For the neural systems and network, the simplest mathematical description is the graph. The new extensive graph may apply to various biological cases on more complexity, in which the cell body corresponds to fields, and axon, dendrite and synapse correspond to various lines.

Chaos Explanation on the Cambrian Explosion

Although the earliest life on Earth was born nearly 3.8-4 billion years ago, the vast majority of the time was found only in single cells, such as bacteria and blue-green algae. When the universe was accelerates, and its energy changes dramatically.

In just millions of years after the beginning of the Cambrian period, a large number of multicellular organisms, including almost all the ancestors of modern animals, which suddenly appeared. It is called the Cambrian Explosion by paleontologists (Gould 1989), and a great mystery in paleontology and geology,

This has attracted many paleontologists and evolutionists to look for evidence to explore its causes, and proposed some hypothesis and theories. For example, Stanley proposed the

cropping principle in ecology, whose main inducing factor is the emergence of algemelagic organisms (Stanley 1979). Lynn Margulis proposed the recombinant reproduction, which is that all eukaryotes evolved from the early symbiogenesis, and that the recombination of symbiotic genes drives the development of biodiversity. Other hypothesis is the developmental regulatory mechanism (Valentine 1971; Valentine et al. 1996). Moreover, there have the conventional ecological hypothesis, and the genomic hypothesis or green genes hypothesis (McMenamin 1989).

Although there are many reasons for the Cambrian biological explosion, it is widely accepted that the sudden increase in oxygen in the Earth's atmosphere was caused. In 1964 L.V. Berkner and L.C. Marshall proposed the oxygen increase hypothesis, in which the multicellular life and animals with more complex metabolism appeared. Abundant oxygen provides the conditions for a big explosion, while the good climate and ecological environment provides the life material base for the biological explosion.

Now one current explanation is that the increase of oxygen reaches 20%. Helium about 25% of the early universe, $\text{He}(2,4) \rightarrow \text{O}(8,16)$ increased four-fold, and $\text{He}(2,4) \rightarrow \text{N}(7,14)$ increased 3.5 times. It corresponds to the key bifurcation point of chaos at 3.75. He essentially disappeared when O and N synthesis. The Cambrian life explosion originated from unicellular to bicellular to multicellular. We propose that the Cambrian explosion can be explained by mathematical chaos.

Cell from 1, to 2 and 4, and air from 2 to 7 and 8 are the iterative equation that reach chaos in the continuous bifurcation of faster and faster processes.

In the biological evolutions the conservation equation is:

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial t} + \text{div}(mv) = 0. \quad (9)$$

If these divergences are bigger, and let $div(mv) = -1 + \lambda m^2$, the equation (9) will become the nonlinear form:

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = 1 - \lambda m^2, \quad (10)$$

its solution is:

$$m = cth(\lambda t) / \sqrt{\lambda}. \quad (11)$$

The social matter and money, etc., will decrease along with time. In this case, Eq.(10) becomes a difference equation:

$$X_{n+1} = 1 - \lambda X_n^2 \quad (12)$$

Assume that the replacement may represent corruptions from one level to another level, or continuous expansive corruption, this equation may be called to a corruption equation. For this, if corruption cannot be controlled effectively, the bifurcation with two periods will appear, and finally, the solution will achieve chaos, namely, whole social system will decompose and become confusion. From quantitative value of bifurcation-chaos, we may estimate that if the corruption members in any social system or a certain level attain to 37.5%, a dangerous double periodic bifurcation will appear. If the members attain to $0.70057759...=70\%$, this system as whole will show an incurable dark. It is some quantitative threshold values for a social system into corruption, and represented visually in a known figure from bifurcation to chaos (Fig.7). This has also fractal character no matter what big or small system, and big or small country.

The evolution of life can be gradual, or it can be the first blowout and then stable screening and evolution according to environmental changes. The Cambrian life explosion involves a variety of factors. It is to become suddenly a large field from simple tree in evolution (Chang 2014b).

Here we discuss only a mathematical result. It must research by methods of different disciplines, so that can better explain the Cambrian life explosion.

Figure 7. Bifurcation-Chaos Diagram

Extensive Quantum Statistics of DNA and Biology

Macromolecules are the basis of life. They are necessary considered as a quantum system in biology. Based on the extensive quantum theory in which the formulations are the same with the quantum mechanics and only quantum constant $\hbar \rightarrow H$, and corresponding basic quantum elements are different (Chang 2002;2018a;2024a), we proposed the extensive quantum biology, in which gene, DNA, RNA, cell, man and any live individual as the smallest live element in various levels are all different live quantum, and discussed the loop quantum theory in biology and general biological string (Chang 2012a). This is the development of Schrödinger theory (Schrödinger 1944), and also corresponds to the wave pattern of biological growth (Levitov 1991; Shipman et al. 2004).

DNA is an important basis of molecular biology (Micklos et al. 2003). A model of DNA is well-known double helical structure. We assumed that A-T and G-C are the basic quantum of DNA, or assume nucleic acid has five types of base quantum: A, T, G, C and U, therefore, we proposed the extensive quantum theory of DNA (Chang 2014a; 2015). For RNA the basic

quantum elements are the corresponding A-U and G-C.

Based on the extensive quantum biology, assume that the basic quantum elements of DNA are A-T and G-C, such the Schrödinger equation with the linear potential may become the Bessel equation. Its solutions are Bessel functions, and may form the double helical structure of DNA in three dimensional spaces. Schrödinger equation at column coordinates and its solution may also derive the double helical structure of DNA. It is necessity mathematical conclusion that quantum mechanics has symmetry (Chang 2022).

The corresponding quantum theory and its many mathematical methods are applied to DNA and molecular biology. From this model we predicted the discrete bound energy spectrum of DNA, and discussed symmetry and supersymmetry of DNA, and researched the entangled state of neurobiology (Chang 2014a), in which A-T and G-C are entangled each other.

20 types of amino acids form proteins, and cells and individuals, etc. Nucleic acid has five types of base quantum: A, T, G, C and U. They as graph theory have only three types of vertex H, N and C. The nitrogenous bases in the opposite strands of DNA always pair in a specific combination: adenine (A) with thymine (T), guanine (G) with cytosine (C). Adenine (A) and guanine (G) are called purine bases as they have two carbon-nitrogen rings. On the other hand, cytosine (C) and thymine (T) are pyrimidines with a single carbon-nitrogen ring.

The deoxynucleotide is the basic units and material basis of Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA). DNA determines biological diversity by the different order of the four bases (T-A) and (G-C) in deoxynucleotides. The four bases are arranged on the inside along the long DNA chain, and their order stores genetic information.

Through the hydrogen bond DNA forms the A-T and G-C base pairing to the double helical structure. The molecular structure of purines is 4N and 5C and that of pyrimidine is 2N and 4C.

Both the purine and pyrimidine rings have a 6-membered component with two nitrogens and

four carbons. Chemical structures of purines (A, G) and pyrimidines (T, C, U) are Fig.8.

Figure 8. Chemical Structures of Purines (A, G) and Pyrimidines (T, C, U)

Guanine is an organic compound with the chemical formula C₅H₅N₅O. It consists of three nitrogen atoms and five carbon atoms with a characteristic double ring structure, and three hydrogen bonds with cytosine. Concurrently present in the in DNA and RNA.

G and C are always paired and complementary, A and T are always paired and complementary (Fig.9). In RNA, A and U are paired in transcription.

Fig.9 G-C and A-T Paired and Complementary

The elements of deoxynucleotide are C (atomic mass 12), H (1), O (16), N (14). It seems to depend mainly on the H number, and the remaining atoms appear in pairs. For DNA, A(3H), G(4H), C(4H), T(5H). Here G-C and T-A are all H=8. For RNA, U(2H).

The bonds for purine and pyrimidines are 14 and 9, respectively, in even and odd numbers.

This has a pairwise and reciprocal periodicity, and agrees to Chargaff parity rule 1.

We generalize the concept of fermions and bosons. Since purines and purines are mutually exclusive, and pyrimidines and pyrimidines are mutually exclusive, both of which are similar to fermions. The purine and pyrimidine are complementary, and the enzyme allows them to bind each other to form the extensive bosons in pairs. This is a further development of the extensive quantum biology to the extensive quantum particles and the extensive quantum statistics. Of course, U is included and can form long chains, resembling bosons.

Table 1. The Extensive Quantum Statistics

Extensive fermion	Spin $s=n+1/2$	Dirac equations	PEP
Extensive boson	Spin $s=n$	K-G equation	BEC

Both have opposite chemical potentials $\mu_F = kT\alpha > 0$ and $\mu_B = -kT\alpha < 0$, and different energy spectra, and different Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distribution laws:

$$n = \frac{1}{e^{\beta\epsilon} \pm 1}. \quad (10)$$

Between the two are the extensive gluons or mesons, which correspond to the chemical bond.

The main material basis of the extensive quantum statistics may be that any matter is composed of charged nuclei and electrons, so they all have magnetic. Paramagnetism attraction, diamagnetism repulsion, both correspond to BE and FD statistics, respectively. They are origin of magnetic moments from the

electron around the nucleus $\mu = -\frac{q}{m}J$ and magnetic moments of particles μ . This is the relation between matter magnetism and extensive quantum statistics. The magnetism of general matter is small, but they may not be negligible for microscopic organisms.

The Dirac equations are:

$$iH \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi = (-ic\alpha H\nabla + \beta mc^2)\psi. \quad (11)$$

Klein-Gordon equation is:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_\mu^2} \psi - \frac{m^2 c^2}{H^2} \psi = 0. \quad (12)$$

Both the Dirac equations and the Klein-Gordon equation are approximated to Schrödinger equation:

$$iH \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \left(-\frac{H^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + U\right)\psi. \quad (13)$$

The time-independent Schrödinger equation is:

$$\Delta \psi + \frac{2m}{H^2} (E - V)\psi = 0. \quad (14)$$

A solution of equation just forms and determines the double helical structure of DNA (Chang 2014a, 2015). It combines the extensive quantum statistics to form periodicity (9) and more detailed structures of DNA.

Its interaction between A-T and G-C complementarity is the hydrogen bond. In this model of DNA, h and m are independent on energy E , potential V , the extensive quantum constant H and mass. It seems to correspond to the universality of DNA. Quantum theory has the axial symmetry that necessarily leads to the DNA. DNA can be considered as an internalization of wave.

Guanine-uracil (G-U) base pairing plays a crucial role in RNA structure. DNA has higher stability and lower synthesis cost, while RNA is known for its structural diversity. One major direction is from DNA to RNA to protein.

We assume that general biology corresponds to the boson fields, since they may be not Pauli exclusion, and possess similar BEC. They possess integral spins, and are quantized with commutation relations leading to Bose-Einstein statistics in the biological extensive quantum theory.

DNA and RNA are the space and the plane, respectively. When T changes U, structure from double helix to plane, and the T and U difference determines the DNA and RNA difference. Statistics and the equations change accordingly.

Benos, et al., began to study the combination of statistical methods and biological principles (Benos et al. 2002). From the extensive quantum biology (Chang 2012a), we may obtain some solutions of the Schrödinger equation, and corresponding energy levels. This obeys the principle of least action. It is related with biological networks and the extensive string theory.

$$(H_{np} + H_{pn}') + (H_{pm}' + H_{mp}) = H_{2(n+m)p}. \quad (15)$$

Its dynamic model is:

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = F_{ip}. \quad (16)$$

It connects with Hopfield model. This is also a matrix mechanics.

For treat, the cancer is similar to bosons, if they are decomposed into fermions, changes to other tissues and is incompatible. This is similar to immunotherapy and genetic modification. It can be combined with nano-therapies.

High temperature treatment for cancer is similar to BEC decomposition at high temperature. Further, various cells can be classified into boson-like and fermion-like based on cell compatibility and exclusion.

Some New Research on Biology

Biology was originally divided into mechanism and vitalism. The new is the organismic biology, whose basic idea is that “the whole is greater than the sum of parts” is origin from the “organizations” or “organizational relations” and interaction relations between “parts”. Woodger proposed that organisms can be explained by chemicals plus “organization relations”, and the concept of “multi-level” structure of organization. Dalcq proposes that life differs from non-living systems by the dynamic and adaptive, etc (Francois 1999).

The important nature of quantum biology is that the results of biological systems are not unique, fully determined, and chance.

All living things on Earth are composed of building modules of four basic molecules: proteins, nucleic acids, polysaccharides and lipids (Ignatova et al. 2003). Benner, et al. (2005a), used natural nitrogen-containing bases to mix eight nucleotides through hydrogen bonding and accepting nucleotides. These nucleotides formed a synthetic genetic system. Currently the genes found are insufficient to reflect the full complexity of the organism. This may be related to non-coding Junk DNA (Benner, et al. 2005b), or even “life originates from RNA molecules”. Perhaps, biological networks should be composed of protein and non-coding RNA dual-color elements. Proteins

dominate the metabolism of modern cells, while nucleic acids dominate their self-replication, both constitute biological complementarity and duality.

In biology there are electromagnetic interactions, and there is biological electromagnetic field. Further, we may research the biological quantum electrodynamics (bio-QED) and the biological chromodynamics (bio-QCD), even the biological quantum flour-dynamics (bio-QFD) (Chang 2024b).

In electromagnetic field Schrödinger equation is:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi' = \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} (\nabla + \frac{e}{\hbar c} A)^2 + e\phi \right] \psi'. \quad (17)$$

The Klein-Gordon equation is:

$$(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} - e\phi)^2 \psi = [c^2 (p - \frac{e}{c} A)^2 + m^2 c^4] \psi, \quad (18)$$

or
$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_\mu} - \frac{ie}{\hbar c} A_\mu \right)^2 \psi - \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \psi = 0. \quad (19)$$

The Dirac equations are:

$$c(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} - e\phi) \psi = \left[-c\alpha (i\hbar \nabla + \frac{e}{c} A) + \beta mc^2 \right] \psi. \quad (20)$$

Further, the biological chromodynamics (bio-QCD) equations are (Heinz 1984):

$$\left\{ \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\mu} + \frac{g}{c} A_\mu \right)^2 + \frac{g\hbar}{2c} \sigma^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\nu} - \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right\} \psi = 0. \quad (21)$$

The wave equation is:

$$(\partial_\mu^2 + m^2) \phi_{in}(x) = 0. \quad (22)$$

Then from a state without interactions to one with interactions as the current form $j(x)$ and self-interactions $\lambda\phi^3(x)$ the equation is (Bjorken et al. 1965):

$$(\partial_\mu^2 + m^2) \phi(x) = j(x) = \lambda\phi^3(x). \quad (23)$$

An approximation of this equation is the Schrödinger equation of stationary state:

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + (E - U) \psi = 0. \quad (24)$$

It can have various solutions.

These are the Yang-Mills equations of bio-QCD, and the mechanical wave theory (Chang 2014d).

Biological and neural networks may apply the scattering Feynman diagram in QCD, etc., and corresponding quantum theory. Such as $ee \rightarrow \text{hardons}$, $hh \rightarrow (ll) + X$. It may apply the inclusive or exclusive process, which focusing on only one channel or all biological outcomes.

Biology forms also the lattice field theory and general lattice theory. Lattice as quantum corresponds to the extensive quantum theory. Based on quantum biology and biological gauge field theory, we proposed the biological lattice gauge theory as modeling of quantum neural networks (Chang 2018b). This method applies completely the same lattice theory in quantum field, but, whose two anomaly problems may just describe the double helical structure of DNA and violated chiral symmetry in biology.

We introduce the quantum field theory in biology, whose goal describes the dynamics of interactions (Bjorken et al. 1965). The S matrix as the scattering matrix is related between in-fields (in-states) and out-fields (out-states):

$$S_{\alpha\beta} = \langle \beta \text{ out} | \alpha \text{ in} \rangle. \quad (25)$$

The S-matrix element is the Green's function for the $r=n(\text{out particles})+m(\text{in particles})$ with the external legs removed. According to the principle of least action and the principle of maximum simplicity (Bjorken et al. 1965), from this determines the folding of amino acids and proteins (Dobson 2003; Stewart 2011), and the biological quantum field theory is constructed.

In a word, various levels in the biological systems have all laws with randomness and statistics, for which the most similar physical theory will be general quantum theory.

Conclusion

Biomathematics is a developed direction of modern biology. We research two new mathematical methods in biology. The Cambrian life explosion can be explained by chaos. We propose the extensive quantum statistics of DNA and biology, whose main material basis may be that any matter has paramagnetism or diamagnetism. Further, we discuss the biological QED, QCD and the extensive quantum biology.

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